

Smart Predictive Digital Twins for Real-Time optimization of Wastewater Treatment Plants.

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Abstract — Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are among the highest energy-consuming infrastructures in urban systems, with over 233 GWh consumed annually across the sector. Their operational inefficiency, compounded by climate-induced inflow variability and stricter environmental regulations, require intelligent and adaptive solutions. This PhD research proposes a Smart Predictive Digital Twin (SPDT) as an innovative methodology to dynamically optimize WWTP operations in real-time, using advanced data analytics and machine learning. The SPDT system integrates data-driven models with physics-informed engineering knowledge to forecast influent behavior and simulate plant responses. Model Predictive Control (MPC) algorithms will close the loop between prediction and action, optimizing energy usage while ensuring effluent quality and environmental compliance. The architecture is modular, comprising global models for system-level forecasting and local models for each treatment stage (e.g., aeration, sludge digestion), to ensure scalability across diverse plant configurations. Real-time sensor integration and IoT infrastructure enable dynamic data acquisition, essential for robust control strategies.

This work will outline the methodological roadmap, research questions, architecture design, control strategies, and validation plan. It will also highlight how the research aligns with several UN Sustainable Development Goals, particularly clean water, energy efficiency, and climate resilience. By bridging data science with mechanical and environmental engineering, this project introduces a scalable, intelligent, and sustainable operational paradigm for modern wastewater treatment systems.

Keywords — Water Systems; Wastewater Operation; Machine Learning; Digital Twin; Cost and Energy Reduction; Climate Change Impact;

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REFERENCES

- [1] I. C. for Resource Recovery from Water, “Circular economy: Tapping the power of wastewater.”
- [2] G. Sabia et al., “Energy saving in wastewater treatment plants: A methodology based on common key performance indicators...,” *Energy Conversion and Management*, vol. 220, 2020.
- [3] J. F. de Canete et al., “Control and soft sensing strategies for a wastewater treatment plant using a neuro-genetic approach,” *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, vol. 144, 2021.